

AUDITORIYA MASHG'ULOTLARIDA KOUCHING TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH

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Annotatsiya:

Ushbu maqolada auditoriya mashg'ulotlarida kouching texnologiyalaridan foydalanish usullari, kouching texnologiyasi mazmuni, uning shakllari va vositalari to'g'risida so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: auditoriya mashg'ulotlari, kouching texnologiyalari, kommunikativ ta'lim texnologiyasi, matnni tushunish texnologiyasi, o'yin texnologiyasi.

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Ingliz tilini o'rganishda ta'lim sifatini oshirish va talabalarning motivatsiyasini oshirish uchun o'qituvchilar interfaol metodlardan foydalanish tavsiya etiladi. Masalan, podkastlar, elektron doskalar, onlayn jurnallar (bloglar), ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, videokonferensiyalar, maxsus mobil ilovalar va boshqalar. O'qituvchining zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalaridan foydalanishi to'rtta nutq faoliyati (o'qish, tinglash, yozish va gapirish) bo'yicha talabalarni sifat jihatidan yangi bosqichga olib chiqishga imkon beradi. E.N.Voronovanning fikriga ko'ra, o'qituvchining chet tilini o'qitishda quyidagi texnologiyalarni joriy etish mumkinligi qayd etilgan:

- kommunikativ ta'lim texnologiyasi;
- matnni tushunish texnologiyasi;
- o'yin texnologiyasi;
- hamkorlik texnologiyasi;
- loyiha texnologiyalari va hokazo [121 s.]².

"Lingvistika" magistratura mutaxassisligining 1-bosqichida majburiy fanlardan "Ilmiy tadqiqot metodologiyasi", "Zamonaviy lingvistika", "Matn lingvistikasi", "Lingvistik tahlil metodlari", "Ilmiy va kasbiy faoliyatga yo'naltirilgan chet tili" fanlari hamda tanlov fanlardan "Tili o'rganilayotgan mamlakat zamonaviy adabiyoti", "Qiyosiy stilistika", "Xorijiy tillarni o'qitish qiyosiy metodikasi", "O'quv kurslarni loyihalash va baholash" fanlari o'rganildi. 2-bosqichda esa majburiy fanlardan "Ilmiy tadqiqot metodologiyasi", "Maxsus fanlarni o'qitish metodikasi", "Qiyosiy tilshunoslik" hamda tanlov fanlardan "Madaniyatlararo muloqot nazariyasi va amaliyoti" fani tahlil etildi.

"Xorijiy til va adabiyoti" magistratura mutaxassisligining 1-bosqichida majburiy fanlardan "Ilmiy tadqiqot metodologiyasi", "Madaniyatlar qiyosiy tipologiyasi", "Kasbga yo'naltirilgan ingliz tili", "Lingvodidaktik tadqiqot metodlari", "O'quv kurslarini loyihalash va baholash", "Chog'ishtirma lingvistika" hamda tanlov fanlardan "Xorijiy tillarni o'qitish

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² Лебедева М.В., Печищева Л.А. Применение современных образовательных технологий в обучении иностранным языкам (На примере английского языка). *Вестник Московского государственного областного университета. Серия: Педагогика.* 2016;(2):120-125. <https://doi.org/10.18384/2310-7219-2016-2-120-125>

qiyosiy metodikasi”, “Chet tilini o‘qitishda baholash mezonlari”, “Zamonaviy lingvistika yo‘nalishlari”, “Tilshunoslikda zamonaviy konsepsiyalar”, “Chet tilini o‘qitishda zamonaviy texnologiyalar”, “O‘quv platformasida onlayn kurslarni yaratish va loyihalashtirish”, “O‘quv kurslarni olib borish amaliyoti” fanlari o‘rganildi. 2-bosqichda esa majburiy fanlardan “Maxsus fanlarni o‘qitish metodikasi”, “Kasbga yo‘naltirilgan ingliz tili” hamda tanlov fanlardan “Matn va diskurs tahlili” fani tahlil etildi.

“Lingvistika” magistratura mutaxassisligi bo‘yicha “Yetti qadamli *self-coaching* strategiyasi”, «Donishmand bilan muloqot», “*SUCCESS*”, “*STEPPA*”, “*+CSMARTE*”, “*CIGAR*”, “*FUEL*” kouching texnologiyalari loyihalashtirildi. “Xorijiy til va adabiyoti” magistratura mutaxassisligi bo‘yicha “Yetti qadamli *self-coaching* strategiyasi”, «Score», “Muvozanat g‘ildiragi”, “GoMAD”, “Haqiqat”, “CLEAR” kouching texnologiyalari loyihalari ishlab chiqildi.

“Yetti qadamli *self-coaching* strategiyasi” texnikasi uchun materiallarni tanlashda quyidagi mezonlarga asoslanildi:

yetti qadam uchun mutaxassislikka qarab fanlarni tanlash;

7 qadamlar uchun mazmunlarini aniqlash (*Take responsibility for your life! Know who you are? Live the present! Clear up your past! Live from the heart! Decide what you want! Empower yourself!*);

qadamlar mazmuni uchun savollar tizimini bosqichlar asosida ishlab chiqish;

strategiyani baholash mezonlarini ishlab chiqish;

strategiyaning dastlabki va yakuniy natijalarini tahlil qilish.

1-bosqich “Xorijiy til va adabiyoti” magistratura talabalariga “Kasbga yo‘naltirilgan ingliz tili” fanidan yuridika sohasiga oid terminlar “Yetti qadamli *self-coaching* strategiyasi” texnikasi loyihalashtirildi (2.6-jadvalga qarang):

2.6-jadval.

Yuridika sohasiga oid terminlar “Yetti qadamli *self-coaching* strategiyasi” texnikasi loyihasi

Qadamlar	Qadamlar mazmuni	Beriladigan savollar
1-qadam	Hayotingiz uchun javobgarlikni o‘z zimmangizga oling!/ <i>Take responsibility for your life!</i>	1) <i>Are you ready to take responsibility for your actions?</i> 2) <i>Is the law foreground in your local area?</i>
2-qadam	O‘zingizni bilib oling!/ <i>Know who you are?</i>	1) <i>Do you know what is the legal profession?</i> 2) <i>What is the responsibility of lawyers?</i> 3) <i>What are your strengths and weaknesses in your job?</i> 4) <i>How can you use your strengths?</i> 5) <i>How can you correct your weaknesses?</i>
3-qadam	Bugungi kunda yashang!/ <i>Live the present!</i>	1) <i>Are the services of lawyers topical nowadays?</i> 2) <i>How important is the legal profession in the contemporary society?</i>
4-qadam	O‘tmishni tozalang!/ <i>Clear up your past!</i>	1) <i>Do you have unfinished trials?</i> 2) <i>Do you have failures in your career?</i>
5-qadam	Yurakdan yashang!/ <i>Live from the heart!</i>	1) <i>Do you like your job?</i> 1) <i>Did you make right decision in the choice of your profession?</i>
6-qadam	Nima istayotganingizni hal	1) <i>Are you on the side of law and justice?</i> 2) <i>Who did you decide to protect?</i> 3) <i>Are you focused on your goals?</i>

	qiling!/ <i>Decide what you want!</i>	4) <i>Are your personal goals connected with your professional mission?</i>
7-qadam	O'zingizni mustahkamlang!/ <i>Empower yourself!</i>	1) <i>Do you work on yourself to improve professional skills?</i> 2) <i>What do you do to be a demanded lawyer?</i> 3) <i>Do you learn something from the experienced lawyers and judges?</i>

1-bosqich "Lingvistika" magistratura talabalariga "Ilmiy va kasbiy faoliyatga yo'naltirilgan chet tili" fanidan tibbiyot sohasiga oid terminlar "Yetti qadamli self-coaching strategiyasi" texnikasi loyihalashtirildi (2.7-jadvalga qarang):

2.7-jadval.

Tibbiyot sohasiga oid terminlar "Yetti qadamli self-coaching strategiyasi" texnikasi loyihasi

Qadamlar	Qadamlar mazmuni	Beriladigan savollar
1-qadam	Hayotingiz uchun javobgarlikni o'z zimmangizga oling!/ <i>Take responsibility for your life!</i>	1) <i>Are you ready to work in such a responsible sphere as medicine?</i> 2) <i>Are you ready to take responsibility for the lives of patients?</i>
2-qadam	O'zingizni bilib oling!/ <i>Know who you are?</i>	1) <i>Do you have enough knowledge of your own specialization?</i> 2) <i>What are your job responsibilities?</i> 3) <i>What are your strengths and achievements?</i> 4) <i>What are your main weaknesses?</i>
3-qadam	Bugungi kunda yashang!/ <i>Live the present!</i>	1) <i>Can you use the modern medical technologies in your activity?</i> 2) <i>What are the modern requirements to doctors?</i>
4-qadam	O'tmishni tozalang!/ <i>Clear up your past!</i>	1) <i>Did you have failures and mistakes in the process of curing the patients? Could you correct them?</i> 3) <i>Could you overcome difficulties and fears within your work experience?</i>
5-qadam	Yurakdan yashang!/ <i>Live from the heart!</i>	1) <i>Do you enjoy working as a doctor?</i> 2) <i>Do you get satisfied after the successful recovery of your patients?</i>
6-qadam	Nima istayotganingizni hal qiling!/ <i>Decide what you want!</i>	1) <i>Is your main goal at work healing your patients?</i> 2) <i>Are you focused on your goals?</i>
7-qadam	O'zingizni mustahkamlang!/ <i>Empower yourself!</i>	1) <i>Do you work on yourself to improve your professional skills?</i> 2) <i>What do you do to be a demanded doctor?</i> 3) <i>Do you learn something from the experienced doctors of your time?</i>

"Donishmand bilan muloqot" modeli uchun materiallarni tanlashda quyidagi mezonlarga asoslanildi:

mutaxassislikka qarab fanlarni tanlash;

muloqot uchun savollar tizimini bosqichlar asosida ishlab chiqish;
 modelni baholash mezonlarini ishlab chiqish;
 modelning dastlabki va yakuniy natijalarini tahlil qilish.

1-bosqich “Xorijiy til va adabiyoti” magistratura talabalariga “Ilmiy tadqiqot metodologiyasi” fanidan «Donishmand bilan muloqot» texnikasi bo'yicha quyidagi savollar berildi:

1. *What is the topic of your research work?*
2. *What instructional phenomenon is the object of your research work?*
3. *How did you define the subject of your investigation?*
4. *Were you able to identify the topicality and novelty of your research?*
5. *What kind of difficulties do you often have in conducting a research?*
6. *What methods did you use for doing the linguistic research?*
7. *Do you follow the guidance of your scientific advisor?*
8. *What teaching means and methods have you used in your English classes at the experimental stage of your research?*

9. *What are the results of your research work?*
 10. *What contribution do your research findings make to the sphere of foreign language teaching methodology?*

1-bosqich “Lingvistika” magistratura talabalariga “Ilmiy tadqiqot metodologiyasi” fanidan «Donishmand bilan muloqot» texnikasi bo'yicha quyidagi savollar berildi:

1. *What is the topic of your research work?*
2. *What linguistic phenomenon is the object of your research work?*
3. *How did you define the subject of your investigation?*
4. *Were you able to identify the topicality and novelty of your research?*
5. *Have you analyzed enough scientific literature?*
6. *What kind of difficulties do you often have in conducting a research?*
7. *What methods did you use for doing the linguistic research?*
8. *Do you follow the guidance of your scientific advisor?*
9. *What are the results of your research work?*
10. *What contribution do your research findings make to the sphere of linguistic science?*

“Score” modeli uchun materiallarni tanlashda quyidagi mezonlarga asoslanildi:

model uchun mutaxassislikka qarab fanlarni tanlash;

5 bosqich mazmunlarini aniqlash;

bosqich mazmuni uchun savollar tizimini ishlab chiqish;

modelni baholash mezonlarini ishlab chiqish;

modelning dastlabki va yakuniy natijalarini tahlil qilish.

1-bosqich “Lingvistika” magistratura talabalariga “Xorijiy tillarni o'qitish qiyosiy metodikasi” fanidan «Score» modeli loyihalashtirildi (2.8-jadvalga qarang):

2.8-jadval.

“Xorijiy tillarni o'qitish qiyosiy metodikasi” fanidan “Score” modeli loyihasi

“Score” modeli bosqichlari	“Score” modelining mazmun-mohiyati
1-bosqich	<i>What is the goal of analyzing the linguacultural units of two languages?</i>
2-bosqich	<i>What are the peculiarities of linguacultural units of languages?</i>
3-bosqich	<i>What are the reasons of analyzing the linguacultural units of languages?</i>
4-bosqich	<i>What are the results and findings of your analysis?</i>

5-bosqich	Use the model of "Grow"
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1-bosqich "Xorijiy til va adabiyoti" magistratura talabalariga "Madaniyatlar qiyosiy tipologiyasi" fanidan «Score» modeli loyihalashtirildi (2.9-jadvalga qarang):

2.9-jadval.

"Madaniyatlar qiyosiy tipologiyasi" fanidan "Score" modeli loyihasi

"Score" modeli bosqichlari	"Score" modelining mazmun-mohiyati
1-bosqich	What is the goal of teaching the linguacultural units of two languages?
2-bosqich	What are the peculiarities of teaching linguacultural units of languages?
3-bosqich	What are the reasons of teaching the linguacultural units of languages?
4-bosqich	What are the results and findings of your teaching process?
5-bosqich	Use the model of "Grow"

"Muvozanat g'ildiragi" modeli uchun materiallarni tanlashda quyidagi mezonlarga asoslanildi:

- mutaxassislikka qarab fanlarni tanlash;
- mavzuni 8 qismlarga ajratish;
- mavzu qismlarini baholash;
- 8 ta qismlardan 3 ta qismlarni tanlash;
- 3 ta qismlardan 1 ta qismni tanlash;
- 1 ta qismni 8 ta komponentlarga ajratish;
- har bir komponentlarni baholash;
- 3 ta komponentlarni tanlash;
- "Grow" modelida ishlash va suhbatlashish.

"Xorijiy til va adabiyoti" mutaxassisligi 1-bosqich uchun "Lingvodidaktik tadqiqot metodlari" fanidan "Muvozanat g'ildiragi" modeli uchun kouching ish qog'ozi ishlab chiqildi (2.10-jadvalga qarang):

2.10-jadval.

"Lingvodidaktik tadqiqot metodlari" fanidan "Muvozanat g'ildiragi" modeli uchun kouching ish qog'ozi

Talaba hayotda o'zi uchun muhim bo'lgan sakkizta lingvistik bo'limlarini yozing / Write 8 most important branches of linguistics																																							
Lexicology	Morphology	Phonology	Phonetics	Stylistics	Lexicography	Syntax	Etymology																																
Har bir lingvistik bo'limlarini 1 dan 5 gacha bo'lgan miqyosda baholang / Evaluate each branches from 1 to 5.																																							
1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5																				
5					5					5					4					4					3					4					2				
Sakkizta lingvistik bo'limdan talaba eng muhim uchta fanni tanlang / Choose 3 most important branches																																							
Lexicology				Morphology				Syntax																															
Talaba faqat bitta eng muhim lingvistik bo'limni tanlang / Choose only one most important branch																																							
Lexicology																																							

Ushbu lingvistik bo'limni 8 ta komponentga bo'ling / Divide the chosen branch into 8 components.																																															
Semasiology					Phraseology					Word formation					Onomasiology					Lexicography					Diachronic lexicology			Synchronic lexicology			Etyymology																
Yana har bir elementni 1 dan 5 gacha baholang / Evaluate each component from 1 to 5																																															
1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5																							
4					5					5					5					5					4			5			5																
3 ta element tanlang va "Grow" modelida ishlang / Choose 3 elements and analyze them using the model of "Grow"																																															
Phraseology														Semasiology														Word formation																			
G														R														O										W									
Semasiology mavzusida suhbat																																															
The goal of semasiology is to							The role of semasiology is							The opportunity of semasiology is							Advantages of knowing semasiology is																										

“Xorijiy til va adabiyoti” mutaxassisligi 2-bosqich uchun “Maxsus fanlarni o’qitish metodikasi” fanidan “Muvozanat g’ildiragi” modeli uchun kouching ish qog’ozi ishlab chiqildi (2.11-jadvalga qarang):

2.11-jadval.

“Maxsus fanlarni o’qitish metodikasi” fanidan “Muvozanat g’ildiragi” modeli uchun kouching ish qog’ozi

talaba hayotda o’zi uchun muhim bo’lgan sakkizta mutaxassislik fanlarini yozing / Write 8 most important special subjects of Bachelor’s degree																																							
RW				LS				ICT				ISS				IS				DA				Country study				Grammar / Vocabulary											
har bir fanni 1 dan 5 gacha bo’lgan miqyosda baholang / Evaluate each subject from 1 to 5																																							
1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
5				5				5				3				2				4				4				5											
sakkizta fandan talaba eng muhim uchta fanni tanlang / Choose 3 most important subjects																																							
RW														LS														Grammar/Vocabulary											
talaba faqat bitta eng muhim fanni tanlang / Choose only one most important subject																																							
LS																																							
ushbu fanni 8 ta komponentga bo’ling / Divide the chosen subject into 8 components																																							
Pre-listening				While-listening				Post-listening				Listening comprehension				Individual speech				Dialogue				Discussion				Debate											
yana har bir elementni 1 dan 5 gacha baholang / Evaluate each component from 1 to 5																																							
1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
4				5				5				5				5				4				5				5											
3 ta element tanlang va "Grow" modelida ishlang / Choose 3 elements and analyze them using the model of "Grow"																																							

<i>Listening comprehension</i>	<i>Individual speech</i>		<i>Discussion</i>
<i>G</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>O</i>	<i>W</i>
Education mavzusida suhbat			
<i>The goal of education is to</i>	<i>The reality of education is</i>	<i>The opportunity of education is</i>	<i>The future of people depends on education</i>

“SUCCESS” modeli uchun materiallarni tanlashda quyidagi mezonlarga asoslanildi: modelning yetti bosqich uchun mutaxassislikka qarab fanlarni tanlash;

7 bosqichlar uchun mazmunlari (taxminlarni belgilash, shaxsning muammolari va maqsadlarini tushunish, kuchli va zaif tomonlari, harakatlar rejasini tuzish, harakatlar natijasini baholash, kouching bilan o‘zaro munosabatga kirishish, natijalarni sarhisob qilish bosqichlari)ni aniqlash;

bosqichlar uchun takliflar tizimini ishlab chiqish;

modelni baholash mezonlarini ishlab chiqish;

modelning dastlabki va yakuniy natijalarini tahlil qilish.

“Lingvistika” mutaxassisligi 1-bosqich uchun “Zamonaviy lingvistika” fanidan “SUCCESS” modeli talabalarning gapirish ko‘nikmalarini rivojlantirishda berishi mumkin bo‘lgan takliflarini quyidagi bosqichlarda loyihalashtirish tavsiya etiladi (2.12-jadvalga qarang):

2.12-jadval.

1-bosqich uchun “Zamonaviy lingvistika” fanidan “SUCCESS” modeli loyihasi

Bosqichlar	Takliflar
Birinchi bosqich – taxminlarni belgilash. Kouching dasturidan samarali natijalarga erishish nazarda tutiladi. Kouching talabani savollar yordamida bunga olib keladi	<i>From my point of view, we can improve our speaking skills if we</i>
Ikkinchi bosqich – bu shaxsning muammolari va maqsadlarini tushunish orqali imkoniyatlari ochib beriladi. Bu yerda kutilgan natijaga erishish usullari va shartlari belgilangan	<i>The main problems of students while speaking are</i>
Uchinchi bosqich – bu shaxsning kuchli va zaif tomonlari, e‘tiqodlari anglanadi. Ularni maqsadlariga erishishga yo‘naltirilgan	<i>The strengths and weaknesses of students in speaking</i>
To‘rtinchi bosqich – bu belgilaydigan harakatlar rejasini tuzish, maqsadlarga erishishni tavsiflaydi	<i>The steps to improve speaking skills include the following:</i> 1. 2.
Beshinchi bosqich – harakatlar natijasini baholaydi. Ushbu bosqichda belgilangan maqsadlarga erishilganmi va erishilgandan keyin nima o‘zgargani solishtirilib, baholanadi	<i>The possible achievements in the improvements of speaking skills are</i>
Oltinchi bosqich – kouching bilan o‘zaro munosabatga kirishiladi. Kouching talabaga barcha yutuqlari tan olinishini va kelajakda muvaffaqiyatga erishishga	<i>Interaction between the coach (teacher) and student....</i>

xizmat qilishini tushunishga yordam beradi	
Yettinchi bosqich – natijalar sarhisob qilinadi. Natijalar tayanch terminlarni metodlar yordamida tavsiflanadi	<i>The summary of gained results....</i>

“STEPPA” modeli uchun materiallarni tanlashda quyidagi mezonlarga asoslanildi:
 yetti bosqich uchun mutaxassislikka qarab fanlarni tanlash;
 7 bosqichlar uchun mazmunlari(mazmun, maqsadlarni aniqlash, hissiyotlar, idrok etish va tanlash, reja, harakat bosqichlari)ni aniqlash;
 modelni baholash mezonlarini ishlab chiqish;
 modelning dastlabki va yakuniy natijalarini tahlil qilish
 “Lingvistika” mutaxassisligi 1-bosqich uchun “Zamonaviy lingvistika” fanidan “STEPPA” modeli loyihalashtirildi (2.13-jadvalga qarang):

2.13-jadval.

1-bosqich uchun pragmalingvistika mavzusida “STEPPA” modeli loyihasi

Bosqichlar	Bosqichlarning mazmuni
1 bosqich – mazmun bosqichi. Mazkur bosqichda kouching mazmuni va yo‘nalishi aniqlanadi	<i>The meaning and essence of pragmalinguistics as one of the branches of linguistic science:</i>
2 bosqich – maqsadlarni aniqlash bosqichi. Bu bosqichda maqsadga erishish mumkinligi aniqlanadi. Agar yo‘q bo‘lsa, unda kouching o‘z talaba iga savollar yordamida ma‘lum natijalarni beradigan to‘g‘ri maqsadni aniqlashda yordam beradi	<i>The aim and objectives of pragmalinguistics:</i>
3 bosqich – hissiyotlar bosqichi. Talabaning ijobiy yoki salbiy hissiy holati belgilanadi	<i>Your attitude to pragmalinguistics: The advantages of learning pragmalinguistics: The disadvantages of the lack of knowledge of pragmalinguistics:</i>
4 bosqich – idrok etish va tanlash bosqichi. Kouch talabaning muammo va vazifalari idroki kengaytiriladi, har doim tanlov mavjudligi tushuniladi, muvaffaqiyatga olib boriladigan variantlarning har biri batafsil ko‘rib chiqiladi va maqbuli tanlanadi	<i>Think about the components of pragmalinguistics. Choose the most important ones among them</i>
5 bosqich – reja bosqichi. Rejani ishlab chiqishda maqsadi va harakatlari aniqlanadi. Kouch talaba rejani tushunishga, to‘g‘ri ishlab chiqilgani va shaxsiy imkoniyatlari e‘tiborga olingani kelishib olinadi	<i>Work out the plan of learning pragmalinguistics</i>
6 bosqich – harakat bosqichi. Ushbu bosqichda vaqt usuli ishlatiladi, har bir harakat rejaning ma‘lum bir davriga taalluqlidir. Va butun reja qismlarga	<i>Allocate certain amount of time to each step of your plan</i>

bo‘linadi, ularning har biri o‘z maqsadlariga ega bo‘ladi	
7 bosqich – harakat bosqichi. Reja tuzilgandan so‘ng, talaba harakat qilishi kerak, ya‘ni uning rejasini amalga oshirish. Ushbu bosqichda kouch talaba ga faol harakatlanish va qo‘rquvni yengib o‘tishga yordam beradi	<i>Apply your written overview in practice</i>

“Haqiqat” modeli uchun materiallarni tanlashda quyidagi mezonlarga asoslanildi: model uchun mutaxassislikka qarab fanlarni tanlash;

6 bosqich mazmunlari(muammo va uning xabardorligi, muammolarni yechilgandan keyingi natijalar, sabablarini tahlil qilish, qarashlar, harakatlar, yangi xatti-harakatning muvaffaqiyatini tahlil qilish)ni aniqlash;

bosqich mazmunini ishlab chiqish;

modelni baholash mezonlarini ishlab chiqish;

modelning dastlabki va yakuniy natijalarini tahlil qilish.

“Xorijiy til va adabiyoti” magistratura mutaxassisligi 2-bosqich uchun “Haqiqat” modeli bojxona sohasiga yo‘naltirilgan ingliz tiliga loyihalashtirildi (2.14-jadvalga qarang):

2.14-jadval.

“Haqiqat” modeli loyihasi

Bosqichlar	Bosqichlar mazmuni
Muammo va uning xabardorligi bosqichida kouch “Bu vaziyatda nima yomon?”, “Vaziyatni yaxshi tomonga o‘zgartirish mumkinmi?” kabi savollarni berish orqali ta‘lim oluvchilarining muammolarini muhokama qiladi	<i>The degree of awareness in the customs sphere. The negative situations in the customs sphere: The ways of improving the customs sphere:</i>
Muammolarni yechilgandan keyingi natijalar bosqichida ta‘lim oluvchi muammo hal qilingandan keyin nima o‘zgarishi (yaxshi yoki yomon o‘zgarish) haqida o‘ylaydi	<i>The results of studying the customs sphere:</i>
Muammoning sabablarini tahlil qilish bosqichida ta‘lim oluvchi yashirin bo‘lishi mumkin bo‘lgan muammolarning sabablari bilan bog‘liq kouchning ochiq savollariga javob beradi	<i>The causes of typical problems in the customs sphere:</i>
Qarashlar bosqichida ta‘lim oluvchi mo‘ljallangan natijalarga erishish uchun qaysi qarashlar va e‘tiqodlarni o‘zgartirish kerakligini tushunishi kerak	<i>The possible approaches and views that can be used in the process of improving the customs sphere</i>
Harakatlar bosqichi nafaqat ish paytida xatti-harakatlar, balki ta‘lim oluvchining ma‘lum bir ko‘nikma va qobiliyatlari to‘plamidir. Bu yerda axloq modellarini, ishda ko‘nikmalardan foydalanishni muhokama qilinadi	<i>The course of actions aimed at the development of customs</i>

Yangi xatti-harakatning muvaffaqiyatini tahlil qilish bosqichida ta'lim oluvchi belgilangan natijalarga rejalashtirilganidek erishildimi yoki erishilmaganini baholaydi	<i>The analysis of possible results</i>
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“CLEAR” modeli uchun materiallarni tanlashda quyidagi mezonlarga asoslanildi:
vaziyat bo'yicha shartnomani aniqlash;
vaziyatni tinglash;
vaziyatni o'rganish;
vaziyat uchun harakatlar rejasini ishlab chiqish;
vaziyat bo'yicha mulohaza yuritish.

“Xorijiy til va adabiyoti” magistratura mutaxassisligining 2-bosqich talabalari uchun “CLEAR” modeli loyihalashtirildi (2.15-jadvalga qarang):

2.15-jadval.

“CLEAR” modeli loyihasi

C – shartnoma	L – tinglash	E – o'rganish	A – harakat	R – mulohaza
<i>Contract with the department</i>	<i>Following the instructions and directions of the scientific advisor and other teachers of the department</i>	<i>Studying the documents of the department, observing the lessons</i>	<i>Learning and preparing to conduct lessons</i>	<i>Summarizing the findings, thinking about the challenges and ways of preventing them</i>

“CIGAR” modeli uchun materiallarni tanlashda quyidagi mezonlarga asoslanildi:
vaziyatning hozirgi haqiqatini aniqlash;
vaziyat mukammaligiga ishonch hosil qilish;
vaziyat bo'shliqlarini tahlil qilish;
vaziyat bo'yicha harakatlar rejasini ishlab chiqish;
vaziyat bo'yicha mulohaza yuritish.

“Lingvistika” magistratura mutaxassisligining 2-bosqich talabalari uchun “CIGAR” modeli loyihalashtirildi (2.16-jadvalga qarang):

2.16-jadval.

“CIGAR” modeli loyihasi

S – hozirgi haqiqat	I – mukammal	G – bo'shliq	A – harakat	R – mulohaza
<i>Students' basic knowledge about language and discourse</i>	<i>The main components of the discourse</i>	<i>The area of discourse analysis that is vague for students</i>	<i>Applying the theoretical knowledge in practice while accomplishing analytical tasks</i>	<i>Students' thoughts about the importance of the discourse analysis in language learning</i>

“FUEL” modeli uchun materiallarni tanlashda quyidagi mezonlarga asoslanildi:
vaziyatga kirishishga suhbatni tartiblash;
vaziyatning hozirgi holatini tushunish;
vaziyatning istalgan holatini tekshirish;
vaziyat bo'yicha muvaffaqiyatli reja taqdimotini ishlab chiqish.

“Lingvistika” magistratura mutaxassisligining 2-bosqich talabalari uchun “FUEL” modeli loyihalashtirildi (2.17-jadvalga qarang):

2.17-jadval.

“FUEL” modeli loyihasi

F – suhbatni tartiblash	U – hozirgi holatni tushunish	E – istalgan holatni tekshirish	L – muvaffaqiyatli reja taqdimoti
<i>Consultation of the scientific advisor</i>	<i>The object and subject of your research</i>	<i>Analyze the main parts your research</i>	<i>Findings and achievements of your research work</i>

“+CSMARTE” modeli uchun materiallarni tanlashda quyidagi mezonlarga asoslanildi: mutaxassislikka qarab fanlarni tanlash; mazmunlarini aniqlash (*Phrased in positive terms, Controllable, Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant, Timed, Ecological*); mazmun uchun savollar tizimini bosqichlar asosida ishlab chiqish; modelni baholash mezonlarini ishlab chiqish; modelning dastlabki va yakuniy natijalarini tahlil qilish.

“Lingvistika” magistratura mutaxassisligining 2-bosqich talabalari uchun “+CSMARTE” modeli “*Medical terms*” mavzusida loyihalashtirildi (2.18-jadvalga qarang):

2.18-jadval.

“Medical terms” mavzusida “+CSMARTE” modeli loyihasi

<i>Phrased in positive terms</i>	<i>What are the positive sides of learning medical words?</i>
<i>Controllable</i>	<i>How can you control the process of learning medical terms?</i>
<i>Specific</i>	<i>What is the specific field of medicine that interests you?</i>
<i>Measurable</i>	<i>What number of words of medical sphere do you know? What number of words related to medicine do you want to learn?</i>
<i>Attainable</i>	<i>Do you think it is impossible to learn medical terms?</i>
<i>Relevant</i>	<i>In what cases can you use your knowledge of medical terminology?</i>
<i>Timed</i>	<i>How much time do you need to learn the main medical terms?</i>
<i>Ecological</i>	<i>How can the knowledge of medical terminology facilitate your daily lifestyle?</i>

Xulosa qilib aytganda, “Yetti qadamli *self-coaching* strategiyasi”, «Donishmand bilan muloqot», “*SUCCESS*”, “*STEPPA*”, “+CSMARTE”, “*CIGAR*”, “*FUEL*”, «*Score*», “*Muvozanat g’ildiragi*”, “*GoMAD*”, “*Haqiqat*”, “*CLEAR*” kouching texnologiyalarini loyihalashtirishda fanlar bo‘yicha materiallarni tanlash talab etiladi.

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